

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION

Sl. no.	Wt. of saccharin titrated mg	Wt. found with alc. KOH*				Wt. found with t-Bu ₄ NOH*			
		Cond.	Error	Enth.	Error	Cond.	Error	Enth.	Error
1.	0.46	0.488	+5.8	0.488	+5.0	0.448	-2.6	0.408	-11.3
2.	0.92	0.908	-2.8	0.948	+2.6	0.897	-3.8	0.884	-5.0
3.	1.84	1.812	-1.9	1.852	+0.5	1.917	+5.0	1.904	+3.5
4.	3.68	3.744	+1.7	3.664	-0.6	3.754	+2.1	3.742	+1.5
5.	5.52	5.475	-1.0	5.456	+1.2	5.413	+1.9	5.504	-0.4
6.	7.36	7.287	-1.0	7.390	-0.9	7.616	+3.4	7.616	+3.4
7.	9.20	9.820	+1.2	9.098	-1.1	9.452	+2.7	9.452	+2.7
8.	11.04	10.780	-2.8	10.686	-2.2	11.856	+2.9	11.288	+2.2
9.	12.88	12.450	-3.4	12.450	-3.4	13.828	+3.5	13.600	+5.6
10.	14.72	14.124	-4.1	14.080	-4.7	16.184	+9.0	16.320	+10.8
11.	16.56	15.796	-4.7	15.703	-5.8	17.680	+6.8	17.680	+6.8
12.	18.40	16.911	-8.7	17.097	-7.1	20.586	+11.6	20.740	+12.5

* Method: Cond. = conductometric, Enth. = enthalpimetric.

The conductometric titrations were carried out using a Naina digital conductometer with an accuracy of $\pm 1 \mu\Omega^{-1}$. The conductivity cell was conditioned in acetone before use. Enthalpimetric titrations were carried out in an insulated beaker and catalytic polymerisation of acetone was used to detect the end-point⁵.

Procedure: All titrations were carried out as reported earlier⁴. Benzoic acid (A.R.) in acetone was used to standardise both alc. KOH and t-Bu₄NOH and the end-points were determined graphically.

Results and Discussion

Choice of proper titrant: Titration curves for conductometric titrations (not shown) did not show sharp breaks and so the end-point was obtained by extrapolation. The enthalpimetric titration curves showed a sharp break (not shown) at the end-point with a sudden increase of temperature due to polymerisation of anhydrous acetone with a slight excess of the titrant. The results obtained with both the titrants (Table 1) reveal that alc. KOH is a better titrant than t-Bu₄NOH.

Effect of dilution: A constant weight of saccharin was titrated by both the methods at different dilutions. The total volume was varied from 15 to 40 ml in steps. There was no noticeable effect of dilution observed within the limits studied.

Effect of concentration: A stock solution of saccharin in acetone (1.85 mg ml^{-1}) was prepared and different volumes of these solutions (1–20 ml) were diluted to 20 ml with acetone and titrated by these methods and the results are presented in Table 1. Saccharin in the range 1.8–10 mg (0.09 – 0.5 mg ml^{-1}) can be determined with an error less than 2% by conductometric method and in the same range with an error less than 1.2% by enthalpimetric method. The mean and standard deviations were found to be 0.10 and 0.14 for conductometric and 0.09 and 0.098 for enthalpimetric method, respectively.

Both the methods are simple, fast and do not require any sophisticated instruments. The results are reproducible. The advantages of determining saccharin in nonaqueous solvent over aqueous methods are that saccharin is highly soluble in cold acetone and much smaller amount can be determined. However, saccharin is not soluble in cold water so heating or addition of alcohol is required to dissolve it for its determination in aqueous medium.

References

1. P. G. RAMAPPA and A. N. NAYAK, *Analyst*, 1983, 108, 966; C. M. HERNANDEZ, G. I. LOPEZ and P. O. SANCHEZ, *Talanta*, 1985, 32, 825; V. STARVA, *Chem. Listy*, 1985, 79, 992 (*Anal. Abstr.*, 1986, 48, 579).
2. "British Pharmacopoeia", H. M. S. O., London, 1980, Vol. 1, p. 393. "United States Pharmacopoeia XX and N. F. XV", United States Pharmacopoeial Convention, Rockville, 1980, p. 1275.
3. J. KUCHARSKY and L. SAVARIK, "Titrations in non-aqueous Solvents", 2nd. ed., Elsevier, New York, 1974, p. 49.
4. D. S. SABDE and R. B. KHARAT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 53.
5. G. A. VANGHAN and J. J. SWITENBANK, *Analyst*, 1965, 90, 594.

Photometric Determination of Benzidine as Azo Dye in Traces using Salicylic Acid

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BENZIDINE is normally determined just like other aromatic amines¹ and its MAK value could not be established due to high toxicity². The present paper describes a photometric method for its deter-

mination based on its diazotisation and subsequent coupling with salicylic acid.

Experimental

A Cari-Zeiss spektr'ophotometer with 1-cm path-length was used.

A stock solution (1 mg ml⁻¹) of benzidine in 20% ethanol and 0.06 M HCl was prepared. A working standard of 10 µg ml⁻¹ was used. A sodium nitrite solution of 200 µg ml⁻¹ strength was used. A 2% (w/v) solution of salicylic acid was prepared in 0.3 M NaOH. All reagents used were of A.R. grade.

Procedure : To a sample containing 5–25 µg of benzidine in 10-ml volumetric flask, sodium nitrite solution (1 ml) and 2 M HCl (1 ml) were added in succession and the mixture was left for 2 min. Then solutions of salicylic acid (1 ml) and 4 M NaOH (0.5 ml) were added and the volume was made upto the mark with demineralised water. The solution was kept for 10 min at room temperature for full colour development and the absorbance was measured at 480 nm against water.

Results and Discussion

The orange dye having maximum absorbance at 480 nm was stable for ~48 h.

Acidity : 1 min was sufficient for complete diazotisation in presence of 0.2–5 M HCl. An amount of 0.3–0.6 ml of 4 M NaOH in 10 ml sample was needed for full colour development.

Analytical characteristics : Beer's law was obeyed in the concentration range 0.5–2.5 ppm with molar absorptivity of $5.7 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and Sandell's sensitivity $0.0032 \text{ µg cm}^{-2}$, respectively. The standard deviation and coefficient of variation were found to be 0.006 and 1.04% respectively for 10 µg of benzidine in 10 ml of the solution.

Effect of foreign species : The tolerance limits (in ppm) for various foreign species associated with benzidine (1 ppm) are as follows : *p*-Nitroaniline, *o*-nitroaniline, phenol (5), aniline, formaldehyde (25), nitrobenzene, chlorobenzene (100), *o*-, *m*-, *p*-nitrotoluene, diphenylamine, pyridine (160), hydrocarbons (1000) : Al^{III}, Cu^{II} (160), Ba^{II}, Pb^{II}, Fe^{III}, Cr^{III} (150), Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, chloride, nitrate, phosphate, sulphate (300) ; metal ions forming hydroxide in alkaline medium were masked with 1 ml of 10% Na₂-EDTA. Some amines interfered but in high concentration.

Application : The method can be reliably applied for the determination of benzidine in urine and polluted water samples with ~95% and ~100% of recovery, respectively.

Data in Table 1 presents the superiority of this method over the reported ones^{3,4}.

TABLE 1

Method	λ_{max} (nm)	Molar absorptivity $\times 10^4 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$
α -Naphthol ^a	585	4.48
8-Hydroxyquinoline ^b	500	3.80
Salicylic acid ^c	480	5.70

^a Ref. 3. ^b Ref. 4. ^c Present work.

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References

1. J. T. STEWART, T. D. SHAW and A. B. RAY, *Anal. Chem.*, 1969, **41**, 860 ; G. NORWITZ and P. N. KELLER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1982, **54**, 807.
2. F. A. PATTY, "Industrial Hygiene and Toxicology", Interscience, New York, 1968, Vol. II, p. 2138 ; W. LEITHE, "The Analysis of Air Pollutants", Ann Arbor Science Publishers, Ann Arbor, 1971, p. 248 ; I. M. KOLTHOFF, P. J. ELVING and F. H. STROSS, "Treatise on Analytical Chemistry", Wiley Interscience, New York, 1971, Part III, Vol. 2, p. 144 ; P. F. MEAL, J. COOKER, H. K. WILSON and J. N. GILMOUS, *Br. J. Ind. Med.*, 1981, **38**, 191.
3. P. VERMA and V. K. GUPTA, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1988, **151**, 261.
4. S. UPADHYAY and V. K. GUPTA, *Am. Ind. Hyg. Assoc. J.*, 1985, **46**, 524.

Isolation and Identification of Barbiturates in Biological Material by Thin Layer Chromatography

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THIN layer chromatography has been widely used as a rapid and simple screening method for phenobarbital¹. The present paper describes a rapid method for the identification and estimation of barbiturates by means of tlc and its application towards the study of barbiturates in biological fluids. The process of isolation and identification is based on acid hydrolysis of barbiturates. The derivatives are analysed by tlc.

Standard tlc equipment and A. R. grade reagents were used. Stationary phase was silica gel G (0.25 mm) on glass plates (20 × 30 cm), and mobile phases were methanol-chloroform and benzyl alcohol-